

Allelopathic Effect of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* aqueous Extract on the Growth Rate of *Arachis hypogea*

M.H Kafinga*¹, S.A Danturai¹, M.B Abubakar¹, H. Bilyaminu¹, Abubakar A², Lawal M³, Aminu Y¹

¹Department of Forestry and Wildlife Management, Aliko Dangote University of Science and Technology, Wudil, P.M.B 3244, Kano, Nigeria;

²Department of Forestry and Wildlife Management, Bayero University, P.M.B 3011, Kano, Nigeria;

³Federal University Gashua, Yobe, Nigeria.

*Correspondence: M.H Kafinga (muhsinhassan62@gmail.com).

Abstract

A nursery experiment was conducted to investigate the allelopathic effects of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* on growth variables (seedling height, girth and number of leaves) of *Arachis hypogea* (groundnut). Aqueous leaf extracts of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* (cold and hot water solutions) were used at different rates (0%, 25%, 50% and 100%) as treatment to determine their effects on groundnut. *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* leaf powder was extracted using hot and cold water methods at different concentrations (0g, 25g, 50g, 100g per liter). Hot extraction involved heating for 20 minutes, while cold extraction involved soaking for 2 days. The study employed a 2 x 4 Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 70 polythene bags and 10 replicates per treatment level. The results showed significant inhibition of seedling growth, with the hot treatment (T2, 25 %) exhibiting the highest inhibitory effect in the seedling height (12.120 %), and (T2, 25 %) in the hot treatment showing the highest inhibitory effect in the seedling girth (1.070 %), also hot treatments (T2, 25 % and T4, 100 %) showed the highest inhibitory effect with 36.800 number of leaves in both. The hot *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* aqueous extract had a greater inhibitory effect on the growth rate compared to the cold aqueous extract, the results showed significant variation ($P < 0.05\%$). The study concluded that *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* allelopathy can negatively impact groundnut production. Overall, *Arachis hypogaea* should not be planted in association with *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* trees due to its inhibitory effects (allelopathy) on the plant growth.

Keywords: *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, Allelopathy, *Arachis hypogea*, hot and cold treatments

1. Introduction

Allelopathy is a biological phenomenon that refers to the beneficial or harmful effects of one plant on another plant through the release of biochemical's (known as allelochemicals) through leachates, root exudation, volatilization and residue decomposition in both natural and agricultural systems (Gupta *et al.*, 2007). These, allelopathic substances impede the growth and

germination of neighbouring plant species and these allelochemicals can be found in various parts of a tree plant, in the flowers, the roots, the tree bark, and also in the leaves (Kato-Noguchi, 2021). The phenomenon (Allelopathy) has both positive (beneficial) and negative (harmful) effects, negatively it causes auto toxicity, soil sickness, and it hinders or inhibits the growth and germination of receptor plants, positively it helps in the control of pests and diseases in plant (Bachheti *et al.*, 2020).

Some of these chemicals (allelochemicals) are released into the environment through leaching by dews or rain, litter decomposition, roots exudation or direct volatilization (Gross and Parthier, 1994; Seligler, 1996). These allelopathic tree plants become a cause for great concern when they are present alongside with crop plants. The issue of allelopathy on inhibiting the growth of plants or agricultural crops is alarming (Chu *et al.*, 2014). Due to ignorance the blame mostly goes to the soil and the seed for the poor performance of harvest which in some cases their believe may be true, but on the other hand arises another known cause called allelopathy which is considered to be one of the cause of that decreases biodiversity (Chu *et al.*, 2014). Because of these, harmful trees are knowingly and unknowingly planted or incorporated into the farms.

Eucalyptus camaldulensis been one of these trees have negative impact because it contains allelochemicals. Similar studies have found that inhibitory effects of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* depends on the level of concentration of the extract and litter fall with higher concentration of materials having higher effects and vice versa (Ahmed *et al.*, 2008). Now *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* being the target tree of this research is widely distributed in the study area, and the effect of the allelochemicals present in the tree is very high, but the rate of the effects are unknown. So the rate of these effects is investigated.

The specific objectives of the study are; to investigate the rate of the inhibitory effects of aqueous extracts of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* on Groundnut at different levels of concentrations, to determine the effects of cold and hot methods *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* aqueous extracts preparation on the growth performance of *Arachis hypogea* and to compare the effect of outdoor and indoor experiment on the growth rate of *Arachis hypogea*.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Area

The experiment was conducted at Kano University of science and Technology Wudil, Wudil Local government. The area is located on Latitude 11°51'N and Longitude 9°20' E at an altitude of 430m above sea level (Figure 1). The mean annual rainfall is 800mm with relative humidity of 75% during the rainy season with a mean annual temperature of 26°C (Olofin *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 1: Map of Kano state showing Wudil

2.2 Experimental Procedures

Eucalyptus leaves were collected from young stands, dried under a shed, and then ground into a powder. Three different amounts of the powdered leaves (25g, 50g, and 100g) were measured using digital scale. The extract was prepared in two ways. In the first method (hot) the extract was heated on a mild heat for 20 minutes and dissolved in 1000ml (1 liter) of water for each treatment measured while in the second method, the leaf powder was soaked in 1000ml (1 liter) cold water for two days. After preparation, the results were filtered using a thin fine cotton cloth, and the extract was stored for watering the seedlings twice daily.

The experiment was conducted at the Department of Forestry and Wildlife Management nursery. In each phase (indoor and outdoor) experiments, 70 polythene bags were used. In both the two experiments mentioned above, 30 bags were allocated cold water treatments, another 30 bags were allocated to hot water treatments and 10 bags each serving as the controls (0%) in indoor and outdoor experiment That is, within each treatment (cold and hot) for each phase, 10 replications were assigned to each treatment concentration level (25%, 50%, and 100%) as well as the control.

The polythene bags were filled with a mixture of soil and organic manure (cow dung) in the ratio of 3:1. The mixture was watered for seven days to allow it to stabilize. Seeds were planted at the same time and depth (5-7 cm). Treatments were applied starting from the next day, and readings were taken accordingly from May, 2023 to August, 2023.

2.3 Experimental Design and Treatment

The experiment was conducted using a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD), with 2 x 4 factorial design (cold water and boiled water) and four concentration levels (treatments) of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* aqueous solution (0%, 25%, 50%, and 100%). This design allowed for the evaluation of the effects of both treatment factors and concentration levels on the experimental outcomes.

2.4 Data Collection

Groundnut seeds germination percentage was determined; also the Shoot length (cm), girth (cm), and number of leaves were taken accordingly.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

A 2-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the variability among the treatments. Statistical Analysis System (SAS) software (version 9) was used for the statistical analysis. Means were compared using Least Significant Difference (LSD) at 5% significant level. The soil characteristics and environmental parameters that can influence the results of this research are: Indoor (pH, Moisture, Low humidity, Absence of Light, Low Temperature and Organic matter content can alter allelochemicals effectiveness) and Outdoor (pH, Rainfall, High humidity, Presence of light, Moderate to high temperature and Organic matter content can influence allelochemicals effectiveness).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Seedling Height (Outdoor Experimentation)

3.1.1 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Height (Hot)

Table 1 below shows the outdoor height values of *Arachis hypogea* recorded for four weeks using hot water mixture of aqueous extract of *E. camaldulensis*. The result shows a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the highest plant height was observed in T1 (control) (5.44cm, 10.80cm, 16.32cm and 21.76cm) respectively, followed by T3 (4.12cm, 8.20cm, 12.34cm and 16.42cm), then T4 (3.75cm, 7.48cm, 11.10cm and 15.00cm) and the lowest height value was observed at T2 (3.03cm, 6.06cm, 8.99cm and 12.76cm) respectively. The findings are in line with the research of Wasihun (2012) that showed *E. camaldulensis* has inhibitory effect on the shoot length of some arable crops when compared to the control.

3.1.2 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Height (Cold)

From the outdoor experiment, using cold *Eucalyptus* aqueous solution, the result depicted significant ($P < 0.05$) difference between the treatments (Table 1). In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the highest plant height was recorded in T1 (control) (5.44cm, 10.88cm, 16.32cm and 21.76cm) respectively, followed by T2 (3.97cm, 7.94cm, 11.91cm and 15.43cm), then T4 (3.95cm, 7.74cm, 11.54cm and 15.48cm) and the lowest height value was observed at T3 (3.86cm, 7.72cm, 11.58cm and 15.44cm) respectively. However, in week 3, T3 (11.58cm) happened to

be higher than T4 (11.54cm) and in week 4, T4 (15.48cm) recorded higher than T3 (15.44cm) and T2 (15.43cm).

From the results obtained, the irregularities recorded could be due to the interference of rainfall. Comparing between cold and hot water, there was no noticeable difference in terms of inhibitory effect as *E. camaldulensis* reduce the seedling height of *Arachis hypogea* compared to controls which is in line with the findings of (Wasihun, 2012).

Table 1: Height of the outdoor (Cold and Hot) experimentation for four weeks

Treatment	HO HT	HO HT	HO HT	HO HT	HO CD	HO CD	HO CD	HO CD
	WAP1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4	WAP1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4
T1 (0%)	5.440 ^a	10.890 ^a	16.320 ^a	21.760 ^a	5.440 ^a	10.880 ^a	16.320 ^a	21.760 ^a
T2 (25%)	3.030 ^c	6.060 ^c	8.990 ^c	12.120 ^c	3.970 ^b	7.940 ^b	11.910 ^b	15.430 ^b
T3 (50%)	4.120 ^b	8.200 ^b	12.340 ^b	16.420 ^b	3.860 ^b	7.720 ^b	11.580 ^b	15.440 ^b
T4 (100%)	3.750 ^{bc}	7.480 ^b	11.110 ^b	15.00 ^b	3.950 ^b	7.740 ^b	11.540 ^b	15.480 ^b
SEM	0.264	0.529	0.785	1.058	0.182	0.356	0.544	0.718

Data with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). H O HT is height of outdoor (hot), H O CD is height of outdoor (cold), GT O HT is girth of outdoor (hot), GT O CD is girth of outdoor (cold), NL O HT is number of leaves (hot), NL O CD is number of leaves (cold), H IN HT is height indoor (hot), H IN CD is height indoor (cold), GT IN HT is girth indoor (hot), GT IN CD is girth indoor (cold), NL IN HT is number of leaves (hot), NL IN CD is number of leaves (cold), WAP is week after planting.

3.2 Seedling Girth

3.2.1 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Girth (Hot)

The table 2 below shows the outdoor girth of *A. hypogea* recorded for four weeks using hot mixture of aqueous extract of *E. camaldulensis*. The result shows a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the widest plant girth was observed in T1 (control) (1.81cm, 1.89cm, 2.03cm and 2.17cm) respectively, followed by T3 (1.50cm, 1.22cm, 1.54cm and 1.62cm), then T4 (1.25cm, 1.18cm, 1.37cm and 1.47cm) and the thinnest girth value was observed at T2 (1.10cm, 1.09cm, 1.13cm and 1.07cm) respectively. The reduction in plant girth in the treatments as compared to control is in line with the findings of Rao and Reddy (1984) which showed the inhibitory effect *E. camaldulensis* on growth rate of some legumes.

3.2.2 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Girth (Cold)

Table 2 presented the outdoor experiment of *Eucalyptus* girth under cold aqueous mixture, there was significant ($p < 0.05$) difference the treatment values in weeks 1, 2 and 4. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the widest plant girth was observed in T1 (control) (1.81cm, 1.95cm, 2.20cm and 2.20cm) respectively, followed by T3 (1.62cm, 1.51cm, 1.54cm and 1.52cm), then T2

(1.35cm, 1.42cm, 2.60cm and 1.47cm) and the thinnest girth value was observed at T4 (1.28cm, 1.37cm, 1.37cm and 1.51cm) respectively. However, in week 3, T2 (2.60cm) happened to be wider than T1(2.20cm) and T3 (1.54cm). Also, in week 4, T4 (1.51cm) is wider than T2 (1.47cm). From the results obtained, the irregularities recorded could be due to the interference of rainfall. Between the cold and hot water extract mixture, there was no noticeable difference. Similarly, the reduction in plant girth in the treatments as compared to control is in line with the findings of Rao and Reddy (1984) which showed the inhibitory effect *E. camaldulensis* on growth rate of some legumes.

Table 2: Girth of the outdoor (hot and cold) experimentation for four weeks

Treatment	GTO HT	GTO HT	GTO HT	GTO HT	GTO CD	GTO CD	GTO CD	GTO CD
	WAP 1	WAP2	WAP 3	WAP4	WAP1	WAP2	WAP3	WAP4
T1 (0%)	1.810 ^a	1.890 ^a	2.030 ^a	2.170 ^a	1.810 ^a	1.950 ^a	2.200 ^a	2.200 ^a
T2 (25%)	1.100 ^c	1.090 ^b	1.130 ^c	1.070 ^c	1.350 ^b	1.420 ^b	2.600 ^a	1.470 ^b
T3 (50%)	1.500 ^{ab}	1.220 ^b	1.540 ^b	1.620 ^b	1.620 ^a	1.510 ^b	1.540 ^a	1.510 ^b
T4 (100%)	1.250 ^{bc}	1.180 ^b	1.370 ^{bc}	1.470 ^b	1.280 ^b	1.370 ^b	1.370 ^a	1.510 ^b
SEM	0.090	0.094	0.086	0.085	0.059	0.054	0.595	0.065

Data with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). H O HT is height of outdoor (hot), H O CD is height of outdoor (cold), GT O HT is girth of outdoor (hot), GT O CD is girth of outdoor (cold), NL O HT is number of leaves (hot), NL O CD is number of leaves (cold), H IN HT is height indoor (hot), H IN CD is height indoor (cold), GT IN HT is girth indoor (hot), GT IN CD is girth indoor (cold), NL IN HT is number of leaves (hot), NL IN CD is number of leaves (cold), WAP is week after planting.

3.3 Number of Leaves

3.3.1 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Number of Leaves (Hot)

The below table 3 below shows the outdoor values for the number of leaves of *Arachis hypogea* recorded for four weeks of using aqueous extract (hot) of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*. Significant ($P < 0.05$) difference was observed among the treatments. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the highest number of leaves was observed in T1 (control) (20.80, 41.60, 62.42 and 83.20) respectively, followed by T3 (10.40, 20.80, 31.20 and 41.69), then least was observed in T2 and T4 (9.20, 18.40, 27.60 and 36.80) where both are the same. The reduction in number of leaves in the treatments as compared to the control is in agreement with the findings of Bhaskar *et al.* (1992) who showed the inhibitory effect of *Eucalyptus* on number of leaves of legumes.

3.3.2 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Number of Leaves (Cold)

Table 3 presented the outdoor values for the number of leaves using cold *Eucalyptus* aqueous mixture, the result showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the number of leaves across all the treatment. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the highest number of leaves was observed in T1 (control) (20.80, 41.40, 62.40 and 83.20) respectively, followed by T2 (19.60, 39.20, 58.80 and 78.40), then T3 (14.80, 29.60, 44.40, 59.20) and the least was observed in T4 (13.70, 27.80, 41.20 and 54.80).

The finding is similar to that of Wasihun (2015), which all treatment levels of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* significantly reduced the growth of maize and horicot beans except for that of 10g which is 10% extract. Similarly, the reduction in number of leaves in the treatments as compared to the control is in agreement with the findings of Bhaskar et al. (1992) that showed the inhibitory effect of *Eucalyptus* on some number of leaves of legumes.

Table 3: Number of leaves outdoor (hot and cold) experimentation for four weeks

Treatment	NLO HT	NLO HT	NLO HT	NLO HT	NLO CD	NLO CD	NLO CD	NLO CD
	WAP 1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4	WAP 1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4
T1 (0%)	20.800 ^a	41.600 ^a	62.400 ^a	83.200 ^a	20.800 ^a	41.400 ^a	62.400 ^a	83.200 ^a
T2 (25%)	9.200 ^b	18.400 ^b	27.600 ^b	36.800 ^b	19.600 ^a	39.200 ^a	58.800 ^a	78.400 ^a
T3 (50%)	10.400 ^b	20.800 ^b	31.200 ^b	41.600 ^b	14.800 ^b	29.600 ^b	44.400 ^b	59.200 ^b
T4 (100%)	9.200 ^b	18.400 ^b	27.600 ^b	36.800 ^b	13.700 ^b	27.800 ^b	41.200 ^b	54.800 ^b
SEM	1.243	2.487	3.731	4.975	1.305	2.599	3.921	5.222

Data with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). H O HT is height of outdoor (hot), H O CD is height of outdoor (cold), GT O HT is girth of outdoor (hot), GT O CD is girth of outdoor (cold), NL O HT is number of leaves (hot), NL O CD is number of leaves (cold), H IN HT is height indoor (hot), H IN CD is height indoor (cold), GT IN HT is girth indoor (hot), GT IN CD is girth indoor (cold), NL IN HT is number of leaves (hot), NL IN CD is number of leaves (cold), WAP is week after planting.

3.4 Seedling Height (Indoor Experimentation)

3.4.1 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Height (Hot)

The indoor results height of *Arachis hypogea* recorded for four weeks using aqueous extract (hot) (Table 4). Significant ($p < 0.05$) difference was recorded across the four weeks. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the highest plant height was observed in T1 (control) (8.63cm, 19.06cm, 25.33cm and 30.04cm) respectively, followed by T2 (3.11cm, 5.31cm, 5.52cm and 9.45cm), then T3 (3.17cm, 4.33cm, 4.91cm and 7.98cm) and the lowest height value was observed at T4 (1.14cm, 2.74cm, 2.96cm and 5.56cm) respectively. However, in week 1, T3 (3.17cm) is higher than T1 (3.11cm) and this could be due to variation in measurement. The finding is similar to

the research conducted by Faroz Ahmad *et al.* (2013) whose statement was that 100% concentration of *Eucalyptus* extract has greatest effects among other levels.

3.4.2 Effects of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* on Seedling Height (Cold)

The values of the plant height with cold mixture for four weeks (Table 4). It showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the treatment values across the weeks. In (WAP 1, 2, 3, and 4) the highest plant height was observed in T1 (control) (8.63cm, 19.06cm, 25.33cm and 30.03cm) respectively, followed by T2 (4.26cm, 6.19cm, 7.47cm and 10.23cm), then T3 (2.62cm, 4.13cm, 5.45cm and 8.48cm) and the lowest height value was observed at T4 (1.75cm, 2.72cm, 5.40cm and 8.46cm) respectively. The control (T1) recorded the highest height values. This finding is in agreement to the research conducted by Faroz *et al.* (2013) that 100% concentration of *Eucalyptus* extract had the greatest effect among other levels of lower concentrations.

Table 4: Height of the Indoor (hot and cold) experimentation for four weeks

Treatment	H IN HT	H IN HT	H IN HT	H IN HT	H IN CD	H IN CD	H IN CD	H IN CD
	WAP1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4	WAP1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4
T1 (0%)	8.630 ^a	19.060 ^a	25.330 ^a	30.040 ^a	8.630 ^a	19.060 ^a	25.330 ^a	30.030 ^a
T2 (25%)	3.110 ^b	5.310 ^b	5.520 ^b	9.450 ^b	4.260 ^b	6.190 ^b	7.470 ^b	10.230 ^b
T3 (50%)	3.170 ^b	4.330 ^b	4.910 ^b	7.980 ^b	2.620 ^b	4.130 ^b	5.450 ^b	8.480 ^b
T4 (100%)	1.140 ^b	2.740 ^b	2.960 ^b	5.560 ^b	1.750 ^b	2.720 ^b	5.400 ^b	8.460 ^b
SEM	0.657	1.017	0.909	1.043	0.701	1.117	1.133	1.398

Data with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). H O HT is height of outdoor (hot), H O CD is height of outdoor (cold), GT O HT is girth of outdoor (hot), GT O CD is girth of outdoor (cold), NL O HT is number of leaves (hot), NL O CD is number of leaves (cold), H IN HT is height indoor (hot), H IN CD is height indoor (cold), GT IN HT is girth indoor (hot), GT IN CD is girth indoor (cold), NL IN HT is number of leaves (hot), NL IN CD is number of leaves (cold), WAP is week after planting.

3.5 Seedling Girth

3.5.1 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Girth (Hot)

The indoor girth value recorded for four weeks using hot *Eucalyptus* aqueous extract (Table 5). There is no significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between the treatments in week after planting (WAP 1 and 2) and except for T4 in (WAP 2) which has the lowest girth value of 0.67. Further more significant ($p > 0.05$) difference was noticed between the treatments values in week 3 and 4. The highest and lowest girth value were recorded in T1 (0.90cm, 1.31cm, 1.73cm and 1.80cm) and T4 (0.26cm, 0.67cm, 0.77cm, 0.86cm) in (WAP 1, 2, 3 and 4) respectfully. This research is related to similar findings by Lisanework and Michelson (1993) who noted a decrease in

germination of maize due to applied *Eucalyptus globulus* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* extracts.

3.5.2 Effects of *E. camaldulensis* on Seedling Girth (Cold)

The indoor girth of *Arachis hypogea* as influenced by cold *Eucalyptus* aqueous extract is shown in Table 5. No significant ($p>0.05$) difference recorded in the treatment values in (WAP 1), but significant ($p<0.05$) in WAP 2,3 and 4. The highest girth value was recorded in T1 (control) (0.91cm, 1.27cm, 1.73cm and 1.80cm) the lowest girth value was recorded in T4 (0.53cm, 0.67cm 0.86cm and 0.94cm) in (WAP1, 2, 3 and 4). Similarly, this research is in line with the findings of Lisanework and Michelson (1993) that noted a decrease in germination of maize due to applied *Eucalyptus globulus* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* extracts.

Table 5: Girth of the indoor (hot and cold) experimentation for four weeks

	GTIN	GTIN	GTIN	GTIN	GTIN	GTIN	GTIN	GTIN
Treatment	HT	HT	HT	HT	CD	CD	CD	CD
	WAP1	WAP2	WAP3	WAP4	WAP1	WAP2	WAP3	WAP4
T1 (0%)	0.900 ^a	1.310 ^a	1.730 ^a	1.800 ^a	0.910 ^a	1.270 ^a	1.730 ^a	1.800 ^a
T2 (25%)	0.810 ^a	1.310 ^{ab}	0.960 ^b	1.090 ^b	0.710 ^a	0.800 ^b	0.930 ^b	1.270 ^b
T3 (50%)	0.530 ^{ab}	1.050 ^{ab}	1.040 ^b	1.130 ^b	0.620 ^a	0.680 ^b	0.860 ^b	1.110 ^b
T4 (100%)	0.260 ^b	0.670 ^b	0.770 ^b	0.860 ^b	0.530 ^a	0.670 ^b	0.860 ^b	0.940 ^b
SEM	0.110	0.126	0.109	0.105	0.111	0.115	0.128	0.097

Data with different superscripts are significantly different ($p<0.05$). H O HT is height of outdoor (hot), H O CD is height of outdoor (cold), GT O HT is girth of outdoor (hot), GT O CD is girth of outdoor (cold), NL O HT is number of leaves (hot), NL O CD is number of leaves (cold), H IN HT is height indoor (hot), H IN CD is height indoor (cold), GT IN HT is girth indoor (hot), GT IN CD is girth indoor (cold), NL IN HT is number of leaves (hot), NL IN CD is number of leaves (cold), WAP is week after planting.

3.6 Number of Leaves

3.6.1 Effects *E. camaldulensis* on Number of Leaves (Hot)

The indoor number of leaves value recorded for four weeks of treatment with hot *Eucalyptus* aqueous extract is shown in Table 6. There was significant ($p<0.05$) difference in all the treatment values recorded across the four weeks, in WAP 1, 2, 3 and 4, the highest number of leaves were observed in T1(control) across the four weeks as (11.2, 31.2, 44.8 and 60.4) respectively, while the least value was recorded in T4 (2.4, 11.2, 17.6 and 20) respectively. The results validate the findings of Ibrahim *et al.* (1999) and Khan *et al.* (2007) that reported leaf extract of *Eucalyptus microthecia* delayed and inhibited the growth of some arable crops.

3.6.2 Effects *E. camaldulensis* on Number of Leaves (Cold)

The indoor number of leaves of *Arachis hypogea* as influenced by cold *Eucalyptus* aqueous extract is shown in Table 6. The result showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between the treatments across the four weeks of the experimentation. In WAP 1, 2, 3 and 4 T1 (control) (11.2, 31.2, 42.0 and 60.4) recorded the highest value for number of leaves and T4 (3, 12.4, 20.0 and 20.8) respectively having the least value for number of leaves across the four weeks. For cold water mixture of the experiment, T4 (100%) had more effect on the number of leaves compared to the rest of the treatment, T1 (control) having the highest number of leaves. This research is related to similar articles by Lisanework and Michelson (1993) who noted a decrease in germination of arable crops due to the effects of *Eucalyptus globulus* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* extracts.

Table 6: Number of leaves for the indoor (hot and cold) experimentation for four weeks

Treatment	NL IN HT	NL IN HT	NL IN HT	NL IN HT	NL IN CD	NL IN CD	NL IN CD	NL IN CD
	WAP 1	WAP 2	WAP 3	WAP 4	WAP 1	WAP2	WAP 3	WAP 4
T1 (0%)	11.200 ^a	31.200 ^a	44.800 ^a	60.400 ^a	11.200 ^a	31.200 ^a	42.00 ^a	60.400 ^a
T2 (25%)	6.400 ^b	21.600 ^b	31.200 ^b	39.600 ^b	6.400 ^b	21.200 ^{ab}	25.200 ^b	36.000 ^b
T3 (50%)	6.800 ^{ab}	18.00 ^{bc}	23.200 ^{bc}	29.200 ^c	6.00 ^b	12.800 ^b	17.600 ^b	25.000 ^c
T4 (100%)	2.400 ^b	11.200 ^c	17.600 ^c	20.00 ^c	3.00 ^b	12.400 ^b	20.000 ^b	20.800 ^c
SEM	1.230	2.539	2.873	2.581	1.179	2.809	3.387	2.882

Data with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). H O HT is height of outdoor (hot), H O CD is height of outdoor (cold), GT O HT is girth of outdoor (hot), GT O CD is girth of outdoor (cold), NL O HT is number of leaves (hot), NL O CD is number of leaves (cold), H IN HT is height indoor (hot), H IN CD is height indoor (cold), GT IN HT is girth indoor (hot), GT IN CD is girth indoor (cold), NL IN HT is number of leaves (hot), NL IN CD is number of leaves (cold), WAP is week after planting.

3.7 Correlation for Outdoor Experiment (Hot)

Figure 2 shows the correlation coefficient for the outdoor experiment (hot). The correlation coefficient depicted that the height positively correlated with the number of leaves (0.92) and also positively correlated with the girth (0.120), which means that as the height increases the number of leaves and girth tends to increase also. The correlation coefficient for the number of leaves and the height shows a positive relationship as (0.972), and negatively correlated with the girth (-0.008), it means that as the leaves increase in number the girth decreases. The correlation coefficient between the girth and the height is positive (0.709) and also positive with the number of leaves meaning that as the girth increases the number of leaves and height also increases.

Figure 2: Correlation Analysis for outdoor experiment (hot)

3.8 Correlation for Outdoor Experiment (Cold)

The correlation coefficient of the outdoor experiment (cold) is shown in Figure 3. The correlation coefficient of the heights positively correlated with the number of leaves (0.927), but negatively correlated with the girth (-0.266), meaning that as the height and the number of leaves were increasing the girth reduced. The number of leaves is positively related to the height (0.927) but negatively correlated with the girth (-0.422). The girth is negatively correlated with the height (-0.266) and also negatively correlated with the number of leaves (-0.422), meaning that as the girth reduces the height and the number of leaves also reduces.

Figure 3: Correlation analysis for outdoor experiment (cold)

3.9 Correlation for Indoor Experiment (Hot)

The correlation coefficient of the indoor experiment (hot) is shown in Figure 4. The height is positively correlated with the number of leaves (0.962) and is also positively correlated with the girth (0.915), meaning that as the height and the number of leaves increases the girth also

increases. The number of leaves positively correlated with the height (0.962) and also positively correlated with the girth (0.900), meaning that there is increase in all the parameters. The girth shows positive correlation with the height (0.915) also positive with the number of leaves (0.900), there is increase in all the parameters.

Figure 4: Correlation analysis for the indoor experiment (hot)

3.10 Correlation for Indoor Experiment (Cold)

The correlation coefficient of the indoor experiment (cold) is shown in Figure 5. The correlation coefficient of the height is positively related to the number of leaves (0.964) and also positively correlated with the girth (0.885), this means that as the height increases the number of leaves and the girth tend to also increase. The correlation coefficient between the number of leaves and the height is positive (0.964) and is also positive with the girth which is (0.847). Same goes for the girth also, the correlation coefficient of the girth and the height is positive (0.885) and is also positive with the number of leaves (0.847), this means that as the girth increases the number of leaves and the height also increases.

Figure 5: Correlation analysis for the indoor experiment (cold)

The limitation of this research is that there is lack of phytochemical analysis to investigate the phytochemical composition of the leaves extracts and the Limited environmental conditions as the study was not conducted as a field trial.

4.0 Conclusions and Future Work

Eucalyptus species is claimed that it is notorious for having allelopathic effect on the growth of agricultural crops in its vicinity. Generally, the indoor (laboratory) experiment inhibited the growth performance of the groundnut more compared to the outdoor (nursery experiment) experiment. Moreover, hot *Eucalyptus* aqueous extract inhibited the groundnut growth rate more compared to the cold aqueous solution. Conclusively, the allelochemicals present in the aqueous extract of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* suppressed all the parameters measured (height, girth and number of leaves) in the crop specie studied and thereby increased inhibition with the increase of concentrations of the extract. These findings prove the allelopathic effect of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* on the growth performance of groundnut. The study recommended that:

1. Phytochemical analysis to Identify and quantify the bioactive compounds present in the extracts to understand their role in the observed effects.
2. Field trials experiment to assess the efficacy of the extracts under real-world environmental conditions.
3. Soil and environmental impact assessment as a result of allelochemicals under real-world environmental conditions.

Conflict of Interest

The Author(s) declared that there are no conflicts or competing interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Author Contributions

Muhsin and Sagir have designed this project, collected data and written this article; while all other authors have critically analyzed this article and approved as final

Funding

The Author(s) received no financial support or funding for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Ethical Statements

This research was conducted in accordance with the Code of conduct.

References

- Ahmed, R., Hoque, A. T. M. R., & Hossain, M. K. (2008). Allelopathic effects of leaf litter of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* on some forest and agricultural crops. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 19(1), 19–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11676-008-0003-x> [Hep Journals](#)
- Bachheti, A., Sharma, A., & Bachheti, R. K. (2020). Plant allelochemicals and their various applications. In J.-M. Mérillon & K. G. Ramawat (Eds.), *Co-evolution of secondary metabolites* (pp. 441–465). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96397-6_14
- Bhaskar, V., Arali, A., & Shankar, B. C. A. (1992). Alleviation of allelopathic effects of Eucalyptus hybrids through litter burning. In *Proceedings of the National Symposium on Allelopathy in Agro-ecosystems*. Proceedings presented at the First National Symposium on Allelopathy in Agroecosystems.
- Chaojun, C., Mortimer, P. E., Heong, K. L., Wang, A., Wang, Y., Liu, X., & Yu, S. (2014). Allelopathic effects of eucalyptus on native and introduced tree species. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 323, 79–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2014.03.004>
- Ebrahim, E. E., Mohammad, H. A., & Mustafa, A. F. (1999). Allelopathic effect of Eucalyptus and *Conocarpus* plantation on germination and growth of two plant species. [*Sudan Journal of Agricultural Research* (2), 9-14
- Faroz, A. A., Rao, R. J., & Mamta, K. (2013). Allelopathic effects of aqueous extracts of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus citriodora*) on the growth and germination of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* var. desi). *Journal of Environmental Science and Engineering Technology*, 1(1), 42–45. <https://doi.org/10.12974/2311-8741.2013.01.01.5>
- Gross, D., & Parthier, B. (1994). Novel natural substances acting in plant growth regulation. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*, 13, 93–114.
- Gupta, B., Thakur, N. S., & Das, B. (2007). Allelopathic effect of leaf leachates of *Pinus roxburghii* Sargent on seeds of some grasses. *Indian Forester*, 133, 997–1000.
- Kato-Noguchi, H. (2021). Phytotoxic substances involved in teak allelopathy and agroforestry. *Applied Sciences*, 11(8), 3314. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11083314>
- Khan, M. A., Hussain, I., & Khan, E. A. (2007). Effect of aqueous extract of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* L. on germination and growth of maize. *Pakistan Journal of Weed Science Research*, 13, 177–182.
- Lisanework, N., & Michelsen, A. (1993). Allelopathy in agroforestry systems: the effects of leaf extracts of *Cupressus lusitanica* and three *Eucalyptus* spp. on four Ethiopian crops. *Agroforestry Systems*, 21, 63–74.
- Olofin, E. A., Nabegu, A. B., & Dambazau, A. M. (2008). *Wudil within Kano region: A geographical synthesis* (Undergraduate thesis). Kano University of Science and Technology.

Rao, N. S., & Reddy, P. C. (1984). Influence of phytotoxin from *Pinus rigida* on selected plants. *Journal of Natural Sciences*, 5, 19–27.

Seigler, D. S. (1996). Chemistry and mechanisms of allelopathic interactions. *Agronomy Journal*, 88, 876–885.

Wasihun, R. (2013). *Allelopathic effects of Eucalyptus camaldulensis and Eucalyptus grandis on Phaseolus vulgaris and Zea mays* (Master's thesis). Hawassa College of Agriculture Nursery site, Hawassa University, Ethiopia.